

Functional structure of mathematical physics

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Summary

Mathematical analysis of the functional process of "expansion" of the Hydrogen atom made it possible to establish a certain dependence of the contour periodic polar limits formed due to the reduction in the charge number. As a result of comparisons with the mathematical data of the actual numerical values of protons and neutrons of all isotopes of chemical elements, the regularity of the relationship between the polar limits of "compression" and "expansion" under the conditions of atomic circuits was contours. These data revealed and expanded the Mössbauer effect, replacing the external impact of elastic resonance with natural internal functional transitions, proton - neutron, neutron - proton, from parent to daughter nuclei. As a result, the functional sequence of these transitions revealed a discrepancy between the orders of chemical elements, between the periodic table of Mendeleev, and the sequence order of the composition of the functional structure of the charge of Hydrogen. Based on these data, the functional structures of each proton and neutron of a separate isotope of the chemical symbol were compiled. Thus, a reorientation process was established - a functional process that determines the polar structure of a charge unit, consisting simultaneously of positive and negative values, located in different compositions of numerical nucleons. This is cold synthesis - the synthesis of the internal functional structure, which is in variable conditions of functional interactions between the limits of the processes of "compression" and "expansion", the internal and external content of the contour of the unit of nucleon limits.

• **Keywords:** number theory, nuclear functions, functional synthesis, phase limits, functional structures, nuclear reorientations, nuclear transitions.

• **Introduction**

This topic relates to identifying the next development of scientific data in the field of research on the origin of matter. The external influence of the "observer" by his understanding of the material world, in the classical view, implies relative perception, as the language of the equivalent of energy. In other words, to give the value a certain energy component that allows you to effectively evaluate the visible results of experiments. Indeed, "A" and "B" will be incompatible objects without the conditions of their logical connection. But if, between "A" and "B" is the energy equivalent of these values "C", then it already becomes a material object. It is possible that this material is the next extreme in the process of cognition of the material world around us. Perhaps because the cycle of material polar limits has no evolutionary phase periods. In turn, there is a cycle of periodic evolutionary structures of functional and phase interactions of these limits.

• **Purpose of research**

Based on the fundamental data of past scientific discoveries and the latest international research publications in the field of searching for the synthesis of new, still unknown materials, as well as, for the conditions for the further development of the science of cognition, still unknown laws of the material world, the purpose of the proposed study is to determine the relationship between internal functional processes of "compression" and "expansions" occurring directly in the numerical structures of all known isotopes of nuclear symbols.

• **Material and research methods**

The information of numerical values and their mathematical operations determines the basis for the interaction of the limiting manifestations of fragments of the numerical structures of a single matter. This is the case when any number contains a projection of the contour of the limits of the general matter. These conditions, which form the meaning of the "core", constitute a distinguished structural contour of the outer cycle of the content of the polar limits. Compared to the classical definition of the nucleus of an atom, the limits of the charge formation structure, in terms of coacervation, do not have orbital electron-positron dipoles. In this case, the charge is the relationship of the polar limits of the internal and external content, the contour of the process of reorientation of the functional structure of these values. Here, the charge is the "center" of compatibility and reorientation of the positive and negative relationship of the composition of the functional structure.

Thus, the composition of the charge structure simultaneously determines the limit of the process of "compression" and the limit of the process of "expansion" of the external and internal content of the space contour unit. Thus, the elementary cyclic sequence of the composition of the content of all known nuclear symbols is within the cycle of the binary charge of known Helium nuclei, from ${}_2\text{He}^3$ to ${}_2\text{He}^8$. This is due to the fact that the external contour of this cycle is Hydrogen, the functional structure of which unit charge is the internal content of the connection of the unity of matter. Here, the materialization of space is defined within the two limits of the outer contour of the zero and the inner content of the structure of the unit. In the proposed topic, any natural number is a contour symbol of a separate fragment, a projection of the structure of the content of a single matter. In this case, unit - the difference of fragments of projections determines the value of the displacement of the limits of the functions of elementary particles of protons and neutrons, which are in the compositions of odd mass numbers. In the case of compositions of even mass numbers, the displacement of fragments of the projections of the limits of protons and neutrons will correspond to zero. This is what concerns integer mass numbers. This method is based on a numerical combination of logical definitions without taking into account known units of energy. This concept will be replaced by a function - a constant action of a numerical cyclic system between the limits of the contour structure of the numerical projections of space. Since these values largely coincide with the fundamental data of physical quantities, the symbols of these definitions are used as tools for the general perception of the structure of the material world. For this it follows that the parts of the unity of the whole are in inverse fractional dependence with respect to the mass number. In other words, the greater part of the empirical mass unit is the smaller mass number, and vice versa, the smaller part of the empirical mass unit is the greater part of the mass number. The determination of the real numbers of protons and neutrons in each isotope of the nuclear symbol made it possible to establish the features of functional interactions in the complex structures of numerical complexes between the limits of the functions of these values, which are in constant processes of reorientation. The formation of structures of numerical compositions, according to the data of their own structural contents of numerical events - numerical fragments of functional projections that determine the actual contour numbers in the form of contour arguments, reveals the mechanism of "manipulation" of the structural sequence of the functional limits of these values.

In this case, successive periods of the compositions of these limits are also functional arguments for the content of the structure of projections of periodic limits. Thus, the static structure of a particular nucleon contains all the isotopes of that nuclear symbol. The composition of the arguments of any functional structure determines the mass number and the number of arguments. The main functions of protons and neutrons give the values of the external and internal contents of the argument structure, that is, the mass number.

The main data of the structure of the arguments are periodic periods - the moments of phase exchanges between the main functions of the arguments of the structure. These are internal processes that determine the properties of the contour of limits, as a fragment of the projection of the unity of matter. Thus, the result of the synthesis of functional projections is the polar values of the limits of the structure of the arguments in the contour. As an example, the synthesis of light stable mirror nuclei of Oxygen, Nitrogen, Carbon and Helium is proposed.

For this, the number of events of each function argument is used. The principle of this method highlights the individual functional structure of the argument of each function in the process of reorientation, which determines the value of the charge structure. In this case, the results of the outer and inner limits of the synthesis arguments are used. It should be said that the proposed demonstration of the method refers to the sequence of formation of nuclear circuits in the process of "expansion" of the Hydrogen charge structure. As you can see, "expansion" and not "compression", which is "proud" of official science, in particular, the well-known thermonuclear fusion. In the case of the "expansion" process, the structure of Hydrogen consistently reduces its charge, by about half, for the conditions for the synthesis of a stable mirror nucleus of Oxygen. In this process, the projection of the unit is reflected. It is known that one, to the power minus one, as well as to any power, is one. In terms of functional structure, this rule does not exist. In the section "Material and Research Methods" it was said that: "The elementary cyclic sequence of the content of all known nuclear symbols is within the binary charge of Helium nuclei, from ${}^2\text{He}^3$ to ${}^2\text{He}^8$. But how was the Helium structure formed? Numbers game! A combination of numerical values and "focus", how to make a three out of one? These are fractions, when the values of two functional limits determine the structure of one number. Any mass number can be written as a fraction, the arguments of which determine the numbers of compositions of protons and neutrons. First of all, it is a part of the whole, that is, a unit. From the point of view of official ideas about the content of mass numbers, this is a paradox: $2/1 = 1/2$. In this case, the values of the main fundamental functions of the proton and neutron are used. From the point of view of these arguments, the presented equality corresponds to a moment of functional reorientation in the condition of "ideal" symmetry. The correction of these "mirror" or "chiral" fractions is introduced by the inequality: $\mathbf{mp} \neq \mathbf{mn}$. It follows from the arithmetic operation of "subtraction" that the result of this operation already selects two protons and the argument of the difference of these bond limits: $\mathbf{mn} + \mathbf{mp} = 2\mathbf{mp} + (\mathbf{mn} - \mathbf{mp})$. But, this is arithmetic! Under conditions of functional interactions, the numerical structures of these arguments remain unchanged, that is: $\mathbf{mp} \neq \mathbf{mp}'$. The state of the sum of the given arguments, under the conditions of functional interactions, produces the corresponding projections of the internal and external structure of the contour of its content. In this case, these projections do not depend on the inequality conditions for these values. The functional structure of any mathematical connection of arguments forms a periodic order of processes that determine the dynamics of cyclic interaction.

Thus, "energy" should not be applied to a number, since any mathematical operation assumes this function in the form of projections of numerical interactions. The processes of forming the contours of the projections of the systemic and structural compositions of the arguments are the energy limits of the functional values.

It follows from this that, for example, the operations of addition and subtraction, in contrast to arithmetic rules, form a structure of argument conflicts in the form of a functional structure, the center of which is the result - a period that contains positive and negative limits of the interaction of arguments. In this case, the arithmetic sum and difference of these arguments will always be constant.

This is due to the fact that the functions of the contours:

$$((A+B)/A)^{-1}, ((A+B)/B)^{-1}, ((A-B)/A)^{-1}, ((A-B)/B)^{-1}, ((A*B)+A)^{-1}, ((A*B)+B)^{-1}, ((A/B)-A)^{-1}, ((A/B)-B)^{-1}, ((A/B)+A)^{-1}, ((A/B)+B)^{-1}$$

So the functions of the contours determine the internal structures of the cyclic interaction of the arguments of the limits of the extreme values, the periods of the processes of "compression" and "expansion". In this case, the mathematical action, in the contour of the structure, and outside of this contour, is presented in the form of a functional projection - a "mirror" function of perception of the structure of the content of interactions of the limits of the conditions for the formation of a unit of space.

▪ Here: **A** → **mn (1,008665012)**, **B** → **mp (1,00727647)**

The relation to the sum or difference of these arguments determines the state of the "expansion" trend. The product of the sum or difference of these arguments determines the state of the tendency to "compress" the structure of the interaction of the main functions. This projective state of tendencies is the energy of the result of the interactions of the main functions. In the conditions of the cycle, all possible interactions occur simultaneously in one circuit of the limits of the main functions. In this case, the cycle of the functional structure of the contour of limits contains a periodic composition - a quantitative component of the structure of the polar limits of the contour of interactions.

For example, the functional projection of the interrelation of a fragment of the period of the process of "expansion" of the posture of the difference of arguments: $((A-B)/A)^{-1}$ and $((A-B)/B)^{-1}$, represents the quantitative content of the same difference with respect to each argument.

From the point of view of phase definitions, this period corresponds to the formation of the gas phase, which is simultaneously in opposite functional limits of the contour of this projection. In this case, a "charge" is formed - the core and the projection of the core of the general periodic functional structure. Here, the projection of the nucleus is the energy of the limits of the charge structure, which determines the value of the displacement as part of unity - the sum of the contours of the function arguments:

- $((\mathbf{A}-\mathbf{B})/\mathbf{A})^{-1}$ and $((\mathbf{A}-\mathbf{B})/\mathbf{B})^{-1}$.
- $((\mathbf{A}-\mathbf{B})/\mathbf{A})^{-1} = 725.4202394$
- $((\mathbf{A}-\mathbf{B})/\mathbf{B})^{-1} = 726.4202394$
- $726.4202394 / 725.4202394 = (\mathbf{A} / \mathbf{B}) = \mathbf{mn} / \mathbf{mp}$
- $((\mathbf{A}-\mathbf{B})/\mathbf{B})^{-1} - ((\mathbf{A}-\mathbf{B})/\mathbf{A})^{-1} = 1$
- kernel $\rightarrow 725.4202394^{-1} = 0.001378511$; nuclear projection $\rightarrow 726.4202394^{-1} = 0.001376614$
- kernel $\rightarrow 725.4202394^{-1} = (\mathbf{A} / \mathbf{B})^{-1} \rightarrow (\mathbf{mn} / \mathbf{mp}) - 1$

In the first example, the interaction of the basic functions of a proton and a neutron, the process of "expanding" the difference of these arguments through the projection of the degree minus one is presented. The reason for these results is a bias between the number of "squeeze" limit events - kernel units and the number of "squeeze" limit events - units of quantity in the kernel projection. In turn, the limit of "compression" of the difference between the numbers of the event, the nucleus and the projection of the nucleus, corresponds to the number of events of the composition of the content of the "potential" of "compression", that is, the difference between the limits of the nucleus and the projection of the nucleus. In this case, functionally equal limits form the interaction of the nucleus and the projections of the nucleus, as functions of the proton and neutron, that is, they become the limits of the internal and external meaning of the contour structure.

These conditions apply to all functional fragments of the interaction of projection contour limits, "compression" and "expansion" of the sum, "compression" and "expansion" of the difference, the sum of "expansion" and "compression", the difference of "expansion" and "compression".

The main example for the analysis of the proposed method of sequential presentation, the accepted trend of relative "expansion", will be the description of the limits of "compression" and "expansion" in terms of the sum and difference of fragments of functional projections. In any case, these definitions, under the conditions of cyclic interactions of mathematical operations of the main functions of the limits of the proton and neutron circuit, do not leave "random" numerical values.

And so, according to the trend of entropy, fragments of "irreversible functions":

$((\mathbf{A}+\mathbf{B})/\mathbf{A})^{-1}$ and $((\mathbf{A}+\mathbf{B})/\mathbf{B})^{-1}$, indeed refer to the classical representation of the interactions of these arguments within functional projections. It is these values that determine the actual numbers of protons and neutrons in the composition of nucleons. But, in this case, the static value of the sum $(\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{B})$ with respect to the arguments represents the phases of the limits of the main functions. That is, here, these are the conditions of the "expansion" process with respect to each argument. In particular, this is the variable phase of a positive number and a number field,

as reduced numerical and functional projections. This is the result of the interaction of three values in the unit volume structure ($\pi/6$).

For example: $((A+B)/A)^{-1} = \mathbf{fnn}' (0.50034439)$; $((A+B)/B)^{-1} = \mathbf{fmp}' (0.49965561)$

Here, $\mathbf{fnn} \rightarrow$ fragment of the neutron function, $\mathbf{fmp} \rightarrow$ fragment of the proton function.

Naturally, the sum of these fragments will be equal to one.

The real numbers of the neutron and proton of these functional fragments will be the following:

• $2 \mathbf{fnn} = \mathbf{mn} (1.000688781)$; $2 \mathbf{fmp} = \mathbf{mp} (0.999311219)$

As can be seen from these data, the proton number is not an absolute field of the neutron number:

• $\mathbf{mn}^{-1} = 0.999311693 \leftrightarrow \mathbf{mp}^{-1} = 1.000689256$

In this case, the sum of the number and the field of these values will be equal to two.

The third argument corresponds to the degree of freedom, that is, the difference between the reduced protons and neutrons in a given composition. These data are the main definitions of the nucleon number - the shift values of the projections of the main functions of the limits of the internal and external content of the mass number structure. For example, a possible composition combination of the mass number thirteen, ($5 + 8 = 13$):

• $[(5 + 8) / 8]^{-1} \rightarrow 0.615384615 / 13^{-1} = 8$

• $[(5 + 8) / 5]^{-1} \rightarrow 0.384615385 / 13^{-1} = 5$

• $(0.615384615 - 0.384615385) / 13^{-1} = 3$

Under the conditions of the oxygen isotope ($8\mathbf{O}^{13}$), the projection fragment: (0.615384615) will correspond to the proton function. Projection fragment: (0.384615385) – neutron functions.

In the case of the Bohr isotope ($5\mathbf{B}^{13}$), on the contrary, the projection fragment: (0.384615385) will correspond to the proton function, and the projection fragment: (0.615384615) will correspond to the neutron function. The maximum ratio of functional projections of this mass number will correspond to the nitrogen isotope ($7\mathbf{N}^{13}$).

In this case, the unit - the difference of the fragments of the projections determines the value of the displacement of the projections of the limits of protons and neutrons in the compositions of odd mass numbers. In the case of compositions of even mass numbers, the displacement of fragments of the projections of the limits of protons and neutrons will correspond to zero. This is what concerns integer mass numbers. This is a substantive demonstration of the principle of the proposed method.

▪ **Method arguments**

The formation of structures of numerical compositions, according to the data of their own structural contents of numerical events - numerical fragments of functional projections that determine the actual contour numbers in the form of contour arguments, reveals the mechanism of "manipulation" of the structural sequence of the functional limits of these values. In this case, successive periods of the compositions of these limits are also functional arguments for the content of the structure of projections of periodic limits.

Thus, the static structure of the nucleon contains all isotopes of the nuclear symbol.

For example, the matrix of the numerical structure (**Matrix 1.**) of the limits of the three isotopes of Nitrogen: (${}_{7}\text{N}^{13} \leftrightarrow {}_{7}\text{N}^{14} \leftrightarrow {}_{7}\text{N}^{15}$).

Matrix 1.

Limits of the composition of zero periods in a reorientation structure here the mirror function of nitrogen leads to the equation from three arguments						
P	n/s ^{mn}	n/s ^{mp}	f mn	f mp	st/sv ⁻¹	st/sv
1	0.125	0.1428571	0.466666667	0.533333333	-0.066666667	-15
2	0.125	0.1428571	0.466666667	0.533333333	-0.066666667	-15
3	0.125	0.1428571	0.466666667	0.533333333	-0.066666667	-15
4	0.125	0.1428571	0.466666667	0.533333333	-0.066666667	-15
5	0.125	0.1428571	0.466666667	0.533333333	-0.066666667	-15
6	0.125	0.1428571	0.466666667	0.533333333	-0.066666667	-15
7	0.125	0.1428571	0.466666667	0.533333333	-0.066666667	-15
8	0.125	0.1428571	0.466666667	0.533333333	-0.066666667	-15
9	0.1428571	0.1428571	0.5	0.5	0	✕
10	0.1428571	0.1428571	0.5	0.5	0	✕
11	0.1428571	0.1428571	0.5	0.5	0	✕
12	0.1428571	0.1428571	0.5	0.5	0	✕
13	0.1428571	0.1428571	0.5	0.5	0	✕
14	0.1428571	0.1428571	0.5	0.5	0	✕
15	0.1428571	0.1428571	0.5	0.5	0	✕
16	0.1666667	0.1428571	0.538461538	0.461538462	0.076923077	13
17	0.1666667	0.1428571	0.538461538	0.461538462	0.076923077	13
18	0.1666667	0.1428571	0.538461538	0.461538462	0.076923077	13
19	0.1666667	0.1428571	0.538461538	0.461538462	0.076923077	13
20	0.1666667	0.1428571	0.538461538	0.461538462	0.076923077	13
21	0.1666667	0.1428571	0.538461538	0.461538462	0.076923077	13
sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum
231	3	3	10.46410256	10.53589744	-0.071794872	-42

Matrix 1. Numerical principle matrix (**Matrix 1.**), of three arbitrary isotopes of Nitrogen, demonstrates a general idea of the structure of the limits in the composition of the numbers of events of the main functions of the proton and neutron. The column (**n/s^{mp}**) of the matrix contains the continuous number

of the event (n/s^{mp}) of the Nitrogen charge (7^{-1}). Within periods (**9 - 15**), the composition of numerical events of protons and neutrons corresponds to the mirror nucleus of Nitrogen (${}^7N^{14}$). As a result, the difference in the limits of proton and neutron fragments leads these values to zero. In this case, the composition of the periods of these limits (**9 - 15**) corresponds to the "power" of the reorientation period ($\times$). Naturally, the sums of numerical events of these limits (**9 - 15**) will be (**3.5**) and (**3.5**), with an average value of (7).

Sequential composition of the limits of three nitrogen isotopes: (${}^7N^{13} \leftrightarrow {}^7N^{14} \leftrightarrow {}^7N^{15}$). Eight periods: ${}^7N^{15}$. Seven periods: ${}^7N^{14}$ and six periods: ${}^7N^{13}$. The sum of the periods: **231**. The sum of the composition of the numbers of events of the neutron function: $n/s^{mn} = 3$. The sum of the composition of the numbers of events of the proton function: $n/s^{mp} = 3$.

The sums of the fragments of neutrons and protons: $f^{mn} = 10.46410256$, $f^{mp} = 10.53589744$. Here: $\text{sum}(f^{mn}) + \text{sum}(f^{mp}) = 21$, corresponds to the number of composition of numeric events of the arguments.

Anticipating the sequence of presentation of the proposed topic, it should be said that under the conditions of using the actual numerical values of protons and neutrons, in the compositions of nucleons, the limits presented in this matrix (**Matrix 1.**) correspond to the Nitrogen group (${}^7N^{14}$) and the Carbon group (${}^6C^{13}$) (**Table 1.**).

Table 1.

P	z	el	m	p'	fmp	fmn	st/sv
1	7	N	15	2	0.466323823	0.534154748	-0.067830925
2	14	Si	30	7	0.466323823	0.536747606	-0.070423783
3	21	Sc	45	17	0.466323823	0.532698399	-0/066374576
4	28	Ni	60	15	0.466323823	0.545917556	-0.079593733
5	35	Br	75	35	0.466323823	0.545119215	-0.078795392
6	42	Mo	90	36	0.466323823	0.33051177	-0.066727354
$\times$					$\times$		$\times$
P	z	el	m	p'	fmp	fmn	st/sv
1	6	C	13	4	0.539733040	0.461196127	0.078536913
2	12	Mg	26	9	0.551803873	0.461196127	0.090607746
3	18	Ar	39	27	0.537503873	0.461196127	0.076307746
4	24	Cr	52	20	0.538726950	0.461196127	0.077530823
5	30	Zn	65	22	0.560210123	0.461196127	0.099013996
6	36	Kr	78	46	0.536422921	0.461196127	0.075226794
7	42	Mo	91	36	0.538178873	0.461196127	0.076982746
8	48	Cd	104	47	0.542375302	0.461196127	0.081179175

Table 1. The sum of the ordinal compositions (**6 + 8 = 14**) corresponds to the mass number of the mirror nucleus of Nitrogen (${}^7N^{14}$). In both cases, the polar nuclei represented by the isotopes of Carbon and Nitrogen (${}^7N^{14}$) and (${}^6C^{13}$) form groups, the number of arguments of which corresponds to the limits of the compositions, separated by periods (**9 - 15**) of reorientation of the composition of the limits of the principal matrix (**Matrix 1**).

These conditions are determined by the displacement - the structure of the number of the nucleon itself, due to the process of functional reorientation, the limits of the contour of the periodic composition, ordinal projections, basic functions, real numbers of protons and neutrons. These are complex tensor interactions of ambiguous definitions under conditions of limiting functional structures. Each encoding of structural compositions "informs" the content of variable functions for the formation of reasons for organizing the conditions for its subsequent definition. In this topic, only a small part is allocated to this section, which is necessary for a general idea of cyclic functional processes occurring under different conditions of the same number.

To do this, you can see for yourself how the same number contains completely different functional structures of its value. For example, all the same mirror nuclei, the compositions of the limits of which are taken by eight arguments of various chemical elements of this definition (Table 2.).

Table 2.

N	z	el	m	fmp	fmn	sum (fmp)/fmp	sum (fmn)/fmn	n/s (fmp)/z	n/s (fmn)/z
1	8	O	16	0.499655610	0.500306890	0.125	0.124423599	0.015625000	0.0155529498
2	7	N	14	0.499655610	0.500822961	0.125	0.124551943	0.017857143	0.0177931347
3	6	C	12	0.499655610	0.501273557	0.125	0.124664003	0.020833333	0.0207773339
4	2	He	4	0.499655610	0.500994390	0.125	0.124594576	0.062500000	0.0622972880
5	16	S	32	0.499655610	0.502344390	0.125	0.124930314	0.007812500	0.0078081446
6	20	Ca	40	0.499655610	0.502344390	0.125	0.124930314	0.006250000	0.0062465157
7	14	Si	28	0.499655610	0.503415819	0.125	0.125196772	0.008928571	0.0089426266
8	10	Ne	20	0.499655610	0.509494390	0.125	0.12670848	0.012500000	0.0126708480
				sum(fmp)	sum(fmn)	sum	sum	sum	sum
A				3.997244880	4.020996787	1	1	0.1523065476	0.1520888413
N	z	el	m	fmp	fmn	sum (fmp)/fmp	sum (fmn)/fmn	n/s (fmp)/z	n/s (fmn)/z
1	15	P	30	0.499655610	0.499499229	0.125	0.124504481	0.0083333333	0.0083002987
2	17	Cl	34	0.499655610	0.513287247	0.125	0.127941263	0.0073529412	0.0075259566
3	18	Ar	36	0.499655610	0.499044390	0.125	0.124391108	0.0069444444	0.0069106171
4	19	K	38	0.499655610	0.502959775	0.125	0.125367051	0.0065789474	0.0065982659
5	21	Sc	42	0.499655610	0.499366612	0.125	0.124471425	0.0059523810	0.0059272107
6	22	Ti	44	0.499655610	0.498261057	0.125	0.124195856	0.0056818182	0.0056452662
7	23	V	46	0.499655610	0.499211840	0.125	0.124432846	0.0054347826	0.0054101238
8	24	Cr	48	0.499655610	0.500267467	0.125	0.124695971	0.0052083333	0.0051956654
				sum (fmp)	sum (fmn)	sum	sum	sum	sum
B				3.997244880	4.011897617	1	1	0.051486981	0.05151340

Table 2. As can be seen, the general fragment of the proton projection determines the functional limit in both sets of eight arguments. This data is in the "expansion" phase. The limit of the proton function - the charge of the argument structure is constant for each structure. In turn, the neutron functions form a pulse range between the first and eighth composition periods (A) and between the second and eighth composition periods (B), histograms (A) and (B).

Histogram (A)

Histogram (A) and Histogram (B). Tendencies of the internal functional structure, which is within the contour of the function of the common proton of mirror nuclei. The seventh and eighth periods of the histogram (A), the second and fourth periods of the histogram (B), the limits of the external expression of the "power" of the compositions of functional neutron fragments. In the case of the histogram (A), the specified "power" of the limit of the composition of fragments of the neutron function is between the first and second periods. In the case of the histogram (B), the specified "power", the limit of the composition of fragments of the neutron function, is between the sixth and second periods.

Graphs of the functional structures of these given compositions will be as follows (**Graphs 1 and 2.**)

Graphs 1.

Graph 1. and Graph 2. The combination of the limit of the neutron function of the fifth and sixth periods with the limit of the proton function forms the "core" of the structure of the limits of the internal and external contents of the composition arguments. This is characteristic in that the ${}_{16}\text{S}^{32}$ and ${}_{20}\text{Ca}^{40}$ nucleons have equal numerical values.

The range of composition of sixteen pairs of arguments of the functional limits of mirror nuclei. (**Histogram 1.**) - composition of stable and unstable chemical elements. For example, the "outer" tenth period, Chlorine (${}_{17}\text{Cl}^{34}$), three types of radioactive decay of the "warm" phase before the emission of a proton. The fourteenth "internal" period, Vanadium (${}_{23}\text{V}^{46}$), the last "warm" decay in the composition of its isotopes.

Thus, the limit of the "external" momentum of Chlorine ($_{17}\text{Cl}^{34}$) and the limit of the "internal" momentum of Vanadium ($_{23}\text{V}^{46}$) will correspond to the energy equivalent of the "power" of the contour of the composition of neutron arguments in this structure. (**Graph 2.**) - the composition of the limits of protons forms the "axis" of the charge of a linear periodic "rod", given by the cordites of the space of the structural series. In this case, the order of the sequence of periods is readable, from left to right, is the composition of the process of "expansion" with subsequent interaction with the "cold" phase of the conditional space. In this case, the sums of all limits of the functions of protons and neutrons will be equal to two. From the point of view of functional structures, these sums correspond to the paradox: $2 \neq 2$.

The combination of two compositions (A) and (B), into one common structure, can be represented by a local impulse system of the "chaotic" order of the reduced composition of arguments, (**Graphs 1 and 2.**) In this case, the question arises about the sequence of the given composition of already sixteen arguments.

In the scale space system of contour definitions, these structures can explain the logical connection of separated objects that are in an invisible dependence of interaction. For example, in the form of the following coordinates, (**Diagram 1.**)

Diagram 1.

Diagram 1. *The conditions of the end contours of the compositions of the limits of functional projections depend on the sequence of fragments of proton projections that form the general structure of interactions of all composition arguments.*

The conditions of the end contours of the compositions of the limits of functional projections depend on the sequence of fragments of the projections of protons that form the general structure of interactions of all arguments of the composition. In turn, the limits of the functional projections of neutrons determine the fundamental significance of the external or internal content of the contour interactions of the arguments of the compositions. In any case, the conditions for the formation of limiting contours are related to the pairwise arguments of the compositions of the functional projections of protons and neutrons.

In the composition of the contours, each proton corresponds to the projection of its own neutron and vice versa, each neutron corresponds to the projection of its own proton. This is the fundamental condition for the composition of the nucleon. Thus, the "capture" of space by the contour of functional projections of the composition of protons will correspond to the contour of functional projections of neutrons. In this case, any ratio of the number of protons and neutrons is determined by the structure of the functional projections of these arguments. In particular, under the conditions of sixteen mirror nuclei, the ratio of the pairwise contour limits of the functional projections of protons and neutrons constitutes predominantly the internal structure of the interaction of these arguments. The exceptions are the pairs of the seventh, eighth, tenth and twelfth periods, (**Diagram 2.**) (**Compositions of functional circuits**).

Diagram 2. (Compositions of functional circuits)

Diagram 2. (Compositions of functional circuits). *The periodic contour of the composition of functional projections of protons (blue marker) of mirror nuclei is the outer contour of pair interactions with the inner contour of functional projections of neutrons (brown marker). The seventh, eighth, tenth and twelfth periods form a "crown" in the form of the contour limits of the functional projections of neutrons. The shift of the extreme values of the functional limits leads to the instability of the relationship of paired projections. In this case, the "decay" of pair interactions corresponds to one or another radioactivity of the contour of a given functional limit.*

▪ **Rationale**

The principle of paired compositions of functional circuits refers to the type and form of space organization. The change in the form and shape of the contour objects of space does not depend on the external factor of influence on the composition of the limits of the framework of the functional structure containing the projection relationship of periodic arguments.

So, for example, under the conditions of sixteen periodic limits of opposite orders, the concentration of the interaction of periods: [7 / 10], [8 / 9], [10 / 7], [9 / 8], exchange phases: $((n + n') / n)^{-1}$ and $((n + n') / n')^{-1}$, corresponds to Erbium isotope data (${}_{68}\text{Er}^{165}$), period interaction [7 / 10], block [A]. Block [B], period interaction [8 / 9], corresponds to Chromium isotope data (${}_{24}\text{Cr}^{51}$).

In turn, blocks [C] and [D], which are behind the reorientation period, divide the unity of phase exchanges: $((n + n') / n)^{-1}$ and $((n + n') / n')^{-1}$ into results of individual functional fragments, accompanying projections of protons and neutrons of the Chlorine isotope ($\text{fmp } {}_{17}\text{Cl}^{32}$), phases: $((n + n') / n)^{-1}$, block [C]. Fluorine isotope ($\text{fmn } {}_9\text{F}^{17}$), exchange phases $((n + n') / n')^{-1}$, block [C]. Neon isotope ($\text{fmp } {}_{10}\text{Ne}^{17}$), block [D] and Carbon isotope ($\text{fmn } {}_6\text{C}^{10}$) block [D] (Matrix 2 [X]).

Matrix 2 [X].

n	n'	Matrix 2. [X] "extensions" of the interaction of compounds 16/16					
↓	↑	$((n + n') / n)^{-1}$	$((n + n') / n')^{-1}$	background	1	2	3
1	16	0.058823529	0.941176471	17	$((n + n') / n)^{-1}$		
2	15	0.117647059	0.882352941	8.5	2		
3	14	0.176470588	0.823529412	5.6666667	1.5	2	
4	13	0.235294118	0.764705882	4.25	4		
5	12	0.294117647	0.705882353	3.4	2.5	2	
6	11	0.352941176	0.647058824	2.8333333	1.2	5	
A	↘	f mp ${}_{68}\text{Er}^{165}$	f mn ${}_{68}\text{Er}^{165}$	↙			
7	10	0.41176471	0.588235294	2.4285714	2.333	3	
B	↘	f mp ${}_{24}\text{Cr}^{51}$	f mp ${}_{24}\text{Cr}^{51}$	↙			
8	9	0.47058824	0.529411765	2.125	8		
C	↘	f mp ${}_{17}\text{Cl}^{32}$	f mn ${}_9\text{F}^{17}$	↙			
9	8	0.52941176	0.470588235	1.8888889	1.125	8	
D	↘	f mp ${}_{10}\text{Ne}^{17}$	f mn ${}_6\text{C}^{10}$	↙			
10	7	0.58823529	0.411764706	1.7	1.429	2.33	3
11	6	0.647058824	0.352941176	1.5454545	1.833	1.2	5
12	5	0.705882353	0.294117647	1.4166667	2.4	2.5	2
13	4	0.764705882	0.235294118	1.3076923	3.25	4	
14	3	0.823529412	0.176470588	1.2142857	4.667	1.5	2
15	2	0.882352941	0.117647059	1.1333333	7.5	2	
16	1	0.941176471	0.058823529	1.0625	16	1	
sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum
136	136	8	8	57.472393	59.74	34.53	12

Matrix 2 [X]. Features of the exchange phase: $((n + n') / n)^{-1}$ As can be seen from the periodic results of the phase exchanges $((n + n') / n)^{-1}$ and $((n + n') / n')^{-1}$, the sum of the limits of these values will be equal to eight. In turn, the structure of the content of these definitions will be different. From the point of view of contour formations, a paradox follows: ($8 \neq 8$). The process of formation of a functional system is accompanied by the selection of the background - the result of phase exchanges.

The sequence of structural formations within the general composition of functional arguments suggests a polar division according to the concentration of "central" periods with subsequent coding of background values. In this case, the phase exchange acts $((\mathbf{n} + \mathbf{n}') / \mathbf{n})^{-1}$, form a four-layer background of the transformed arguments in the form of decimal fractions, the periodic sequence of which encodes the value of the compositions of integers, as projections into minus the first degree.

Here, the conversion of integers occurs according to the principle, for example:

$[2/15], ((\mathbf{n} + \mathbf{n}') / \mathbf{n})^{-1}$.

• $0.117647059^{-1} \rightarrow (8.5 - 8) \leftrightarrow 0,5^{-1} \rightarrow 2$.

Interaction background: $[8 / 2] \rightarrow 0.8 \leftrightarrow 0,2 = 1.25 (1 + 4) \leftrightarrow 5$

As in the case of the table of limits of counter numerical orders (**Counter numerical orders of periodic limits**) in the periodic matrix of functional exchanges, in the process of "expansion", a unit is added to the composition of the arguments:

background $\rightarrow ((\mathbf{n} + \mathbf{n}') / \mathbf{n})^{-1} \rightarrow [1 / 16] (0.058823529^{-1} = 17)$.

In the polar limit: background $\rightarrow ((\mathbf{n} + \mathbf{n}') / \mathbf{n})^{-1} \rightarrow [16 / 1] (0.941176471^{-1} = 1.0625 \rightarrow [1 + 16^{-1}])$.

In other words, the phases of the exchange of polar values of the functional limits, in one case, add a period, in the other case, they transfer the value of the functional limit into the background of the interaction of phase exchanges.

In the case of opposite phase exchanges $((\mathbf{n} + \mathbf{n}') / \mathbf{n}')^{-1}$, the background of interactions increases significantly. This occurs due to the degree of freedom between the limits of the extreme values of the arguments of the functions of opposite compositions of the main functions of the proton and neutron. Thus, the phase of exchange $((\mathbf{n} + \mathbf{n}') / \mathbf{n}')^{-1}$ already highlights the seven-layer background of its functional process (**Matrix 3 [X]**).

This definition is consistent with the cyclic composition of all known isotopes of nuclear symbols ranging from Helium ${}^2\text{He}^3$ to Helium ${}^2\text{He}^8$. In this case, the "compression" pole limit is the number of degrees of freedom between the proton and neutron functions of Helium ${}^2\text{He}^3$. In turn, the "expansion" limit is the number of degrees of freedom between the proton and neutron functions of Helium ${}^2\text{He}^8$.

The "conical" feature of the polar limits, obtained as a result of phase exchanges: $((\mathbf{n} + \mathbf{n}') / \mathbf{n}')^{-1}$, synthesizes background projections in the functional structure of Helium ${}^2\text{He}^8$, due to the average phase of the event number limits - the difference in the interaction of the main functions of the proton and neutrons under the conditions of the reorientation process. This is

the case when the event number (**st/sv**) acquires the value of a proton or a neutron in the period of reorientation of functional interactions.

Matrix 3 [X]

n	n'	Matrix 3. [X] "extensions" of the interaction of compounds 16/16									
↓	↑	$((n + n') / n)^{-1}$	$((n + n') / n')^{-1}$	background	1	2	3	4	5	6	
1	16	0.058823529	0.941176471	1.0625	0.063	16	$((n + n') / n')^{-1}$				
2	15	0.117647059	0.882352941	1.1333333	0.133	7.5	0.5	2			
3	14	0.176470588	0.823529412	1.2142857	0.214	4.67	0.6667	1.5	0.5	2	
4	13	0.235294118	0.764705882	1.3076923	0.308	3.25	0.25	4			
5	12	0.294117647	0.705882353	1.4166667	0.417	2.4	0.4	2.5	0.5	2	
6	11	0.352941176	0.647058824	1.5454545	0.545	1.83	0.8333	1.2	0.2	5	
A	↘	$f_{mp\ 68}\ Er^{165}$	$f_{mn\ 68}\ Er^{165}$	↙							
7	10	0.41176471	0.588235294		1.7	0.7	1.43	0.4286	2.3	0.3	3
B	↘	$f_{mp\ 24}\ Cr^{51}$	$f_{mn\ 24}\ Cr^{51}$	↙							
8	9	0.47058824	0.529411765		1.8888889	0.889	1.13	0.125	8		
C	↘	$f_{mp\ 17}\ Cl^{32}$	$f_{mn\ 9}\ F^{17}$	↙							
9	8	0.52941176	0.470588235		2.125	0.125	8				
D	↘	$f_{mp\ 10}\ Ne^{17}$	$f_{mn\ 6}\ C^{10}$	↙							
10	7	0.58823529	0.411764706		2.4285714	0.429	2.33	0.3333	3		
11	6	0.647058824	0.352941176	2.8333333	0.833	1.2	0.2	5			
12	5	0.705882353	0.294117647	3.4	0.4	2.5	0.5	2			
13	4	0.764705882	0.235294118	4.25	0.25	4					
14	3	0.823529412	0.176470588	5.6666667	0.667	1.5	0.5	2			
15	2	0.882352941	0.117647059	8.5	0.5						
16	1	0.941176471	0.058823529	17							
sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	
136	136	8	8	57.472393	6.472	57.7	4.7369	34	1.5	12	

Matrix 3 [X]. Block [B], $f_{mp\ 24}\ Cr^{51}$; $f_{mn\ 24}\ Cr^{51}$, belongs to the group: $8O^{17}$; $16S^{34}$; $32Ge^{68}$; $40Zr^{85}$, one common functional proton fragment.

Then, the Helium charge number becomes the "axis" of the poles of the limit cone: [${}^2He^3 \leftrightarrow {}^2He^8$], and the event number takes on the value of a proton or a neutron. In numerical terms, the result of the functional interaction will be as follows:
 ${}^2He^8 \rightarrow 6\ mn - 2\ mp = 4\ st/sv$ ($f_{mp} \leftrightarrow f_{mn}$) $\rightarrow {}^6C^{10} \leftrightarrow {}^4Be^{10}$, **st/sv** is the degree of freedom. It should be clarified that the provided result is within the limits of the Helium nucleon number and is only a background expression of the structure of the functional interaction of this isotope.

Thus, the entire functional structure of the contour of the polar limits of the composition of sixteen and thirty-two periodic arguments is in the position of axial displacement of the background layers in the process of mutual phase exchanges.

These conditions distribute the functional background density in the overall structure of the polar limits contour. This circumstance explains the "inconsistency" of functional projections separated by periods of concentration of interactions of the main functions of protons and neutrons. While the numbers of functional concentration limits are equal, the internal content of these values is the functional structure, and the ownership of the obtained fragments will be different. In this sense, the conditions of the expansion process contribute to the existence of belonging to "separated" projections.

Indeed, the limits of functional projections: **fmp** ₁₇Cl³²; **fmn** ₉F¹⁷; **fmp** ₁₀Ne¹⁷; **fmn** ₆C¹⁰, leave the potential of the functional "connection" of the following necessary arguments for the synthesis (**Matrix 3 [X]**).

• Definition

For the conditions of analysis of functional structures, on the basis of fundamental scientific data of elementary particles of physical, chemical and genetic values, in this method, the real numbers of protons and neutrons in the compositions of nucleons are used. This definition is related to the established posture of displacement - the result of a process of reorientation of the functional limits of the inner and outer contours of the structure of space. Thus, this value introduces a qualitative correction into the process of interaction of functional projections of protons and neutrons that are in the composition of nucleons. The nucleon number, in this case, replaces the unit, which determines the outer contour of the content of the interaction of functional projections in the processes of phase exchanges between the periodic limits of the main functions of protons and neutrons. The functional structure of the nucleon number contains the information of all isotopes of one separate nuclear symbol. It is this feature that allows you to "separate" and "define" each value of a numerical combination in a numerical functional structure. A characteristic feature of functions can determine different values of the same number in different conditions of its content.

• Result

The conditions above the presented definition form a displacement position in periods of concentration of the limits of the main functions of protons and neutrons, thereby creating a known concentration of interaction of fragments of functional projections. This is what concerns the opposite orders of integers. Under the conditions of complex numbers, the periods of concentration fall on the compositions of the mirror nuclei. In the general structure of the sequence of the proton function, the composition of these nuclei is also in the position of a shift towards "moderate" fusion relative to the separation of "cold" and "hot" determination of the limits of interaction of all compositions of protons and neutrons that are in a single mass system. Considering that the total static number of all known arguments of the mass system is the number of four circles or twice the value of nine to the cubic power: $[2(9^3) = 1440]$.

In this case, the number of events (n/s) of a given quantity will correspond to the value of the limit of interaction of the main functions of the proton and neutron:

$$[(n/s) \rightarrow 1440^{-1} = 0.000694444].$$

Taking into account the correction of functional definitions, this number varies within the quantity: (1448 - 1451). In any case, this is the "minimum" value of the shift of functional projections of proton and neutron fragments:

$$[1/2(mn (1.008665012) - mp (1.00727647)) = 0.000694271].$$

Here we should recall the definition of the projections of the number and the number field from the "Method" section of this topic, where the number field is the projection of the "dark" and "cold" structure of the degree minus one.

And so, the "warm" phase of the limits of the fragments of the functional projections of protons and neutrons relative to the entire composition of nuclear arguments is forty-three periods. The moderate phase of the exchange of mirror fragments of functional projections of protons and neutrons with respect to the entire composition of nuclear arguments is twenty-eight periods. The rest, "cold" phase of the exchange of nuclear arguments is within one thousand three hundred and seventy-seven periods. In percentage terms, these are: "warm" phase three percent, "moderate" phase two percent and "cold" ninety-five percent (**Diagram 3**).

Diagram 3.

Diagram 3. Percentage of the limits of the "warm", "cold" and "moderate" state of the static contour of the space of matter. Here, **2%** is a "moderate" phase of twenty-eight mirror functional projections of nuclear symbols. **3%** - "warm" phase of forty-three isotopes with a minimum number of neutrons. **95%** - the "cold" phase of one thousand three hundred and seventy-seven isobars with a minimum number of protons. In this proportion, only the main limits of these definitions are used.

Thus, from the category of concentration of functional interaction of the limits of the "central" periods of phase exchanges, fragments of projections of the main functions of protons and neutrons pass into the category of coacervate. In this sense, unlike the state of concentration limits, as a result of one specific functional process of "compression" or "expansion", the coacervate contains the whole complex of multifunctional limits that are in one common phase of all possible interactions. This substance - a mixture of the functional structure is in the state of the phase of the internal potential of the compositions of the external nuclear complexes. In turn, each limit of the "cold" and "warm" phases contains its own functional structure of its content. This is a quantitative structure of numerical events of periods separating the functions of protons from neutrons and taken separately. It is this structure that "filters" the values of the future functional limits of protons and neutrons in the composition of nucleons.

An analysis of the results of periodic reorientations, of each main function of a proton or neutron, makes it possible to use these data in the processes of phase determinations of phase exchanges, phase interactions, and phase transitions.

It is in these functional structures that the process of "cold" fusion takes place - synthesis under the conditions of interaction of neutron structures that are in the process of reorientation, when the function of a neutron becomes a function of a proton and vice versa. In this sense, the sequence of the content of the periodic composition is violated with respect to the relationship of functional projections.

In contrast to the "horizontal" interaction of limits, the main functions of fragments of projections of protons and neutrons, the interaction of the "filtration" process, a separate limit, has a "vertical" periodic content of the reorientation process.

In this case, the event number is coded - the number of the quantitative periodic system of one separate function. In other words, the entire "vertical" sequence of the reorientation structure refers to the value of any one function.

For example, blocks [C] and [D], **Matrix 2[✗]** and **Matrix 3[✗]** of "single" functional fragments: **fmp** ₁₇Cl ³², **fmn** ₉F ¹⁷, **fmp** ₁₀Ne ¹⁷, **fmn** ₆C ¹⁰, obtained as a result of the process of interaction of separating phases : $((\mathbf{n} + \mathbf{n}') / \mathbf{n})^{-1}$, $((\mathbf{n} + \mathbf{n}') / \mathbf{n}')^{-1}$.

The main feature of these definitions is the process of internal formation of the polar structure from the conditions of the process of reorientation of the main functions of protons and neutrons. In this case, each proton and each neutron form its specific functional contour of the internal structure of the cyclic content, as an expression of its meaning. For example, fragments of tables of structural compositions of quantitative proton and neutron of mirror Oxygen **8O¹⁶**, **Table 4, Table 5.**

Table 4.**Table 5.**

N	$mn' \text{ } ^{16}\text{O}$	$\text{Ln}(mn')$	$mn' / \text{Ln}(mn')$	N	$mp' \text{ } ^{16}\text{O}$	$\text{Ln}(mp')$	$mp' / \text{Ln}(mp')$
1	1.00061378	0.000613593	1630.745866	1	0.999311219	-0.000689018	-1450.340567
2	1.00000019	0.000613593	1629.745866	2	0.998622201	-0.000689018	-1449.340567
3	0.9993866	0.000613593	1628.745866	3	0.997933182	-0.000689018	-1448.340567
4	0.998773	0.000613593	1627.745866	4	0.997244164	-0.000689018	-1447.340567
5	0.99815941	0.000613593	1626.745866	5	0.996555146	-0.000689018	-1446.340567
6	0.99754582	0.000613593	1625.745866	6	0.995866127	-0.000689018	-1445.340567
7	0.99693222	0.000613593	1624.745866	7	0.995177109	-0.000689018	-1444.340567
8	0.99631863	0.000613593	1623.745866	8	0.994488091	-0.000689018	-1443.340567
9	0.99570504	0.000613593	1622.745866	9	0.993799072	-0.000689018	-1442.340567
10	0.99509145	0.000613593	1621.745866	10	0.993110054	-0.000689018	-1441.340567
1628	0.00229844	0.000613593	3.745866132	1448	0.002301712	-0.000689018	-3.340567207
1629	0.00168484	0.000613593	2.745865864	1449	0.001612694	-0.000689018	-2.340567207
1630	0.00107125	0.000613593	1.745865864	1450	0.000923675	-0.000689018	-1.340567207
1631	0.00045766	0.000613593	0.745865864	1451	0.000234657	-0.000689018	-0.340567207
1632	-0.00015593	0.000613593	-0.25413414	1452	-0.000454361	-0.000689018	0.659432793
1633	-0.00076953	0.000613593	-1.25413414	1453	-0.00114338	-0.000689018	1.659432793
1634	-0.00138312	0.000613593	-2.25413414	1454	-0.001832398	-0.000689018	2.659432793
1635	-0.00199671	0.000613593	-3.25413414	1455	-0.002521416	-0.000689018	3.659432793
1636	-0.00261031	0.000613593	-4.25413414	1456	-0.003210435	-0.000689018	4.659432793
1637	-0.0032239	0.000613593	-5.25413414	1457	-0.003899453	-0.000689018	5.659432793
3258	-0.99785769	0.000613593	-1626.25414	2899	-0.997463868	-0.000689018	1447.659432
3259	-0.99847128	0.000613593	-1627.25414	2900	-0.998152886	-0.000689018	1448.659432
3260	-0.99908488	0.000613593	-1628.25414	2901	-0.998841905	-0.000689018	1449.659432
3261	-0.99969847	0.000613593	-1629.25414	2902	-0.999530923	-0.000689018	1450.659432
3262	-1.00031206	0.000613593	-1630.25414	2903	-1.000219941	-0.000689018	1451.659432
3263	-1.00092565	0.000613593	-1631.25414	2904	-1.00090896	-0.000689018	1452.659432
3264	-1.00153925	0.000613593	-1632.25414	2905	-1.001597978	-0.000689018	1453.659432
3265	-1.00215284	0.000613593	-1633.25414	2906	-1.002286996	-0.000689018	1454.659432
3266	-1.00276643	0.000613593	-1634.25414	2907	-1.002976015	-0.000689018	1455.659432
3267	-1.00338002	0.000613593	-1635.25414	2908	-1.003665033	-0.000689018	1456.659432

Table 4, Table 5. Fragments of periods of the reorientation structure, real numbers of protons and neutrons of the mirror nucleus of Oxygen ^{16}O . The first ten comparative periods are used for information on the successive "expansion" of periodic values, the composition of the polar limits of the numbers of proton and neutron events. The expansion process occurs due to the mutual reduction of the quantitative values of the proton and neutron per unit interval equal to one. The first, ten information periods. Further, the distinguished comparative periods of neutron and proton reorientations are....

• $mn' / \text{Ln}(mn') \rightarrow 0.745865864 \times (-0.25413414) \rightarrow [1631 - 1632]$

• $mp' / \text{Ln}(mp') \rightarrow -0.340567207 \times 0.659432793 \rightarrow [1451 - 1452]$

At the end of the tables, the periods of the limits of the neutron and proton reorientation values, respectively, are highlighted. These are periods equal to twice the periods of reorientations:

• $mn' / \text{Ln}(mn') \rightarrow [1631 - 1632 \leftrightarrow 3262 - 3264]: mp' / \text{Ln}(mp') \rightarrow [1451 - 1452 \leftrightarrow 2902 - 2904],$ respectively.

In contrast to the process of reorientation, the main limits of the functional fragments of the projections of protons and neutrons that are in the composition of nucleons, the reorientation of the quantitative structure of an individual proton and an individual neutron, itself forms the number of the nucleon. So, for example, the sum of the first period, the event number of the Oxygen neutron ${}_8\text{O}^{16}$ and the polar last period of the event number forms the event number of the Carbon nucleon:

$$\bullet [1] (0.000613593) + [3264] (-1.00153925) = -0.000925462$$

The completely negative number of the Carbon nucleon is formed between the even limit periods: $[3262 - 3264]$, in the odd final period: $[3263]$, the number: -1.00092565 .

Negative mass of mirror Carbon (${}_6\text{C}^{12}$): $12(-1.00092565) = -12.0111078$. The process of reorientation changes the signs and the number of numerical events. In turn, the difference between the first period, the number of the event of the neutron of Oxygen ${}_8\text{O}^{16}$ and the last polar period of the event number forms a functional fragment of the projection of the proton of this Carbon (${}_6\text{C}^{12}$):

$$\bullet [1] (0.000613593) - [3264] (-1.00153925) \rightarrow 2.002153024^{-1} \rightarrow \text{fmp}' {}_6\text{C}^{12} = 0.499462323$$

Particular attention should be paid to the limits of the reorientation periods of the quantitative structures of the proton and neutron in **Tables 4 and 5**.

In this case, the number of the proton reorientation period is much less than the neutron reorientation number: $\text{mp} (1451 \times 1452) < \text{mn} (1631 \times 1632)$. Coordinates of the cyclic difference: $(1631 - 1451) = 180$. In other words, the formation of its polar cycle by the proton will be faster than the formation of its polar cycle by the neutron. These data are embedded in the very structure of the reorientations of these values.

For example, the sum of the "first" periods of the quantitative limits of the neutron and proton of mirror oxygen ${}_8\text{O}^{16}$ will be the exact value of the cycle: $1630.745866 + (-1450.340567) = 180.405299$.

In this case, the value of the converted periods of the neutron structure will correspond to:

$$\bullet 1630.745866 - (-1632.25414) = 3263.$$

This corresponds to half the base of the neutron number: $(\exp(3263^{-1}))^2 = \text{mn } {}_8\text{O}^{16} (1.000613121)$.

In turn, the same values of the proton of this Oxygen supplement the cyclic bond in the structure of the common nucleon.

The sum of the "last" periods of the quantitative polar limits of the quantitative structure of the neutron and proton of mirror Oxygen ${}_8\text{O}^{16}$ will be: $(-1632.25414 + 1452.659432) = -179.594708$.

Thus, the ratio of "heat" and "cold", the array of the "compression" and "expansion" limit, as the cyclic content of the proton - the charge of the neutron contour, corresponds to two polar projections, the difference of which will be a full circle: $180.405299 - (-179.594708) = 360$.

The conditions of the sum of these values determine the shift - the posture of a consistent positive perspective - the energy of the relationship of functional projections (a separate topic). As you can see, the shift arises due to the discrepancy between the periodic compositions of the numerical events of the proton and neutron. They are not linear. Consequently, the periodic composition of the proton "tends" to the "expansion" of the limit of the general contour. In turn, the periodic composition of the neutron - to the "compression" of the limit of the general contour. In this case, the action of opposing "aspirations" is defined as the "energy" of the connection of the frame of the periodic limits of "compression" and "expansion".

The result of such an interrelation of the limits of the proton and neutron of mirror Oxygen ${}^8\text{O}^{16}$ is the Helium nucleon.

$$\bullet [1] \text{mn}' / \text{Ln}(\text{mn}') \rightarrow 1630.745866 - [1] \text{mp}' / \text{Ln}(\text{mp}') \rightarrow$$

$$(-1450.340567) = 3081.086433^{-1} = 0.000324561$$

$$\bullet [3264] \text{mp}' / \text{Ln}(\text{mp}') \rightarrow 1452.659432 - [3264] \text{mp}' / \text{Ln}(\text{mp}') \rightarrow$$

$$(-1632.25414) = -3084.913572^{-1} = -0.000324158$$

$$\bullet \exp(0.000324561) \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \text{nykl He}; \exp(-0.000324158) \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \text{nykl He}$$

$$\bullet \text{nykl He} = \exp(-0.000324158 + 0.000324561) \rightarrow 1.00064893 \times 4 = m {}_2\text{He}^4(4.00259571)$$

This example reveals the mechanism of the number and field projection under the conditions of the relationship between the polar limits of the bases of the "cold" and "warm" phases of matter. This is a function when a negative value projects a "background" adequate structure of the "shadow" of the value of a number to a negative degree. Here, the division of matter and anti-matter is not appropriate, since it is one whole. The combination of polar limits, in the circuit of the interaction of "cold" and "warm" phases, is determined by the functional structure of the concept of the charge of these interactions. Thus, the number of a nucleon is a unit of charge of the entire composition of isotopes of a given chemical element.

The conditions laid down in the tables (**Table 4**, **Table 5**.), in the form of a separate static example, explain the principle of combining the periodic limits of opposite actions - the sum and difference of the negative and positive bases of the neutron and proton of the mirror nucleus of Oxygen ${}^8\text{O}^{16}$. In the case of the neutron number, this is the difference: $\text{mn}' - \text{Ln}(\text{mn}')$. In the case of the proton number, this is the action of the sum: $(\text{mp}' + \text{Ln}(\text{mp}'))$.

Naturally, to solve the conditions of practical cold fusion, only the real numbers of protons and neutrons are needed. The usual difference of these arguments is not sufficient to determine the functional displacement of the limits of these values.

The real numbers of each displacement pose will be the positive and negative result of the reorientation processes. The sum of these results corresponds to the base of the number of the displaced positive or negative part of the base of the nucleon - the unit charge of the reorientation limits. The difference in reorientation results corresponds to the base of the nucleon number. In turn, the positive and negative parts of the reorientation periods are the numbers of information events of the following quantitative periodic structures.

In this case, the relationship between the proton and neutron of the mirror nucleus of Oxygen $8O^{16}$, in the periods of their reorientations, due to the total number of nucleons, corresponds to two polar bases of the Carbon nucleon: $[1631] \rightarrow 0.000457658$ and $[1452] \rightarrow -0.00045436$, under the conditions of the difference between these values (light brown marker).

These periods are also consistent within the circle (light gray marker), **Table 6. (fragments of neutron and proton reorientation $8O^{16}$).**

Table 6. (fragments of neutron and proton reorientation $8O^{16}$)

Fragment of neutron structure reorientation							
1631	0.000457658	0.000613593	0.74586613	1631	-0.12378864	-0.00068902	179.65943
1632	-0.00015593	0.000613593	-0.25413387	1632	-0.12447766	-0.00068902	180.65943
Fragment of proton structure reorientation							
1451	0.110904346	0.000613593	180.745866	1451	0.000234657	-0.00068902	-0.3405672
1452	0.110290754	0.000613593	179.745866	1452	-0.00045436	-0.00068902	0.6594328

Table 6. (fragments of neutron and proton reorientation $8O^{16}$)

Fundamental connection of positions, processes of reorientation of functional structures of proton and neutron projections in a periodic matrix. This is what happens simultaneously in both polar structures of the composition of the nucleon - the unit of charge.

The range of functional connection of "counter" limits: $[1631-1632] \leftrightarrow [1451-1452]$ is the shift period of the proton-neutron, neutron-proton transition. In the case of massive complex structures, this range is the period of synthesis of nuclear formations.

• Conclusion

Any base of a number determines the number of these bases in a given number, distributed in the process of subtraction or addition, depending on the positive or negative value of the base. Thus, the number of bases in the number structure is determined by two periods, one is the limit of the positive value and the second is the limit of the negative value. Consequently, the relationship of these limits forms a periodic circuit of the polar structure of the external and internal content of these limits.

For example, if the number of bases of the neutron of Oxygen is $8O^{16}$: $[mn' / \ln(mn')] = 1630.745866$, then the reorientation periods will be $[1631]$ and $[1632]$, respectively, since the fractional part of the number of bases is shifted towards an increase in the "warm" phases. In turn, the "cold" phase will be part of the limit of the next period: $[1630.745866 - 1631 = -0.254134]$.

Consequently, the "warm" phase will be: $[1630.745866 - 1630 = 0.745866]$. In percentage terms, **Diagram 4.**

Diagram 4.

Diagram 4. Percentage of the composition of the charge in the process of reorientation. These are the conditions of entropy, when in the "warm" phase, as a result of functional exchange, the "distribution" of opposite values occurs, due to the general reorientation, when the difference in the limits of the neutron and proton becomes a proton or neutron in the structure of the displacement period. In this case, it is the composition period of 75%. This is a "natural" or spontaneous division, when the orientation of the polar functions is formed in the unit structure: $1 - 75 = 25$, that is, the expansion function "distributes" the connection of two new values, as functional fragments of new protons and new neutrons: $(75)^{-1}$ and $(25)^{-1}$.

The results, in the form of phase exchanges of these interactions, are in blocks **[D]** and **[E]**. In turn, the opposite arguments of the periods are also in the conditions of interaction, block **[F]**. As a result, each argument of the **[D]** and **[E]** blocks interacts with the argument of the **[F]** block. These actions distribute the main functions of protons and neutrons in the form of fragments of projections of the compositions of nuclear symbols.

The results of the functional synthesis of the column **[e1]** end at a period of interactions of opposite orders of eight and twelve **[8-12]** blocks **[A]** and **[B]**. The data obtained as a result of interactions coincide with the content of the fundamental data of the general mathematical cyclic table of all isotopes of chemical elements. Here, the values of the opposite orders **[A]** and **[B]** are the limits of "compression" and "expansion", respectively (**Table 7**).

Table 7.

			$((B+A)/B)^{-1}$	$((B+A)/A)^{-1}$	A / B	$((D+F)/D)^{-1}$	$((D+F)/F)^{-1}$		
A	B	C	D	E	F	f mp	f mn	st/sv	el
1	19	0.333333333	0.75	0.25	0.950	0.441176471	0.558823529	-0.11764706	${}_{49}\text{In}^{111}$
2	18	0.333333333	0.857142857	0.142857143	0.900	0.487804878	0.512195122	-0.02439024	${}_{21}\text{Sc}^{43}$
3	17	0.333333333	0.9	0.100000000	0.850	0.514285714	0.485714286	0.028571429	${}_{18}\text{Ar}^{35}$
4	16	0.2	0.952380952	0.047619048	0.800	0.543478261	0.456521739	0.086956522	${}_{13}\text{Al}^{24}$
5	15	0.2	0.961538462	0.038461538	0.750	0.561797753	0.438202247	0.123595506	${}_{43}\text{Tc}^{98}$
6	14	0.2	0.967741935	0.032258065	0.700	0.580270793	0.419729207	0.160541586	${}_{71}\text{Lu}^{169}$
7	13	0.2	0.972222222	0.027777778	0.650	0.599315068	0.400684932	0.198630137	${}_{36}\text{Kr}^{90}$
8	12	0.2	0.975609756	0.024390244	0.600	0.619195046	0.380804954	0.238390093	${}_{51}\text{Sb}^{135}$
9	11	0.142857143	0.984	0.015625000	0.550	0.641547862	0.358452138	0.283095723	
10	10	0.142857143	0.985915493	0.014084507	0.500	0.663507109	0.336492891	0.327014218	
11	9	0.142857143	0.987179487	0.012820513	0.450	0.686886708	0.313113292	0.373773417	
12	8	0.142857143	0.988235294	0.011764706	0.400	0.711864407	0.288135593	0.423728814	
13	7	0.142857143	0.989130435	0.010869565	0.350	0.738636364	0.261363636	0.477272727	
14	6	0.142857143	0.98989899	0.010101010	0.300	0.767423649	0.232576351	0.534847298	
15	5	0.142857143	0.990566038	0.009433962	0.250	0.798479087	0.201520913	0.596958175	
16	4	0.25	0.984615385	0.015384615	0.200	0.831168831	0.168831169	0.662337662	
17	3	0.25	0.985507246	0.014492754	0.150	0.867900447	0.132099553	0.735800893	
18	2	0.25	0.98630137	0.013698630	0.100	0.907944515	0.092055485	0.815889029	
19	1	0.25	0.987012987	0.012987013	0.050	0.951784596	0.048215404	0.903569192	
		sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	
		4	18.19537391	0.804626091	9.5	12.91446756	6.085532441	6.828935118	

Table 7. For example, the number of synthesis arguments will correspond to four, block [E]. The composition of the limits of opposite orders, for this case of an example, consists of three, five, seven and four charges, that is, conditional: Lithium, Boron, Nitrogen and Helium. Thus, the total amount of charges will correspond to the periodic composition of nineteen periods down and nineteen periods up ordinal numbers. In this case, each charge event number, block [C], interacts with two opposite values of the same period, blocks [A] and [B].

▪ **Accompanying material:**

▪ **Khripkov A. I.** "THE MATHEMATICAL TABLE OF CHEMICAL SYMBOLS" (page. 35)

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